

Rapid laser-induced nanostructuring for yeast adhesion-reducing surfaces using beam shaping with SLM

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ABSTRACT

Controlling microbial adhesion in industrial and healthcare settings is crucial for maintaining hygiene and preventing biofilm formation. This work describes a novel method to efficiently produce yeast adhesion-reducing surfaces using dynamic beam-shaping with a spatial light modulator. At first, the laser-induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS) topography was tuned to test microbial adherence in a variety of LIPSS configurations, specifically using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* as a model organism. A novel and robust dual-pass laser strategy was implemented to create hierarchical LIPSS structures with periodicities of 630 nm and 5 μm. The integration of dynamic beam shaping with spatial light modulator (SLM) significantly enhanced production efficiency, achieving a throughput of up to 150 cm²/min. The laser-structured surfaces exhibited a significant reduction in yeast adhesion, with a decrease of 95% in adherent cells and achieving a maximum reduction of 99.88%. These findings offer promising implications for developing advanced surface treatments to improve hygiene in industries such as food processing and healthcare, where minimizing microbial colonization is vital.

1. Introduction

Surface functionalization helps in establishing the intrinsic value of a variety of industrial products by affecting how the surface interacts with its surroundings. Modified friction, adhesion, wettability, self-cleaning, optical and aesthetic qualities, cell growth, and microbial retention [1–3] are just a few of the properties that can be added to conventional materials by smart surface functionalization using artificial surface micro and nanostructures [4,5]. The ability to manage microbial retention is particularly relevant for industries where biofilm formation poses challenges, such as food processing and healthcare [6–8]. The search for effective, non-antibiotic strategies to control microbial adherence has gained importance with the increasing concern over antibiotic resistance and the limitations of chemical antibacterial treatments [9,10]. The complexity of microbial adhesion is influenced by numerous factors such as surface topography, material composition,

and surface charge [11,12]. Prior to the formation of cell clusters and multicellular biofilms, microbes adhere to surfaces in a dispersed manner [13]. Surfaces with features smaller than the adhering microorganisms are known to reduce the likelihood of attachment due to decreased contact area [14–16]. Common bacterial cell dimensions are frequently less than 1 μm. For instance, the rod-like *Escherichia coli* has an average size of about 0.5 μm × 2 μm, covering an area of approximately 1 μm², while the spherical *Staphylococcus aureus* covers an area close to 0.25 μm² [17]. Yeast cells are usually oval and larger than 1 μm. For example, the average size of *Candida glabrata* is 1–4 μm and of *S. cerevisiae* 3.5–5 μm. While much research has focused on bacterial adhesion, the study of yeast adhesion, specifically involving *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, offers unique insights. *S. cerevisiae* serves as an important model organism due to its well-documented genetics and similarities to more complex eukaryotic cells. Its larger cell size, typically 3.5–5 μm [18,19], compared to bacteria, makes it an ideal

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candidate for exploring the effectiveness of nanostructured surfaces and their potential to mitigate microbial attachment. Such studies provide foundational data that can be extrapolated to other microbial species and guide the development of surface treatments applicable across various industries, including food and beverage production and medical device manufacturing [20,21].

In this context, ultrashort pulsed laser irradiation presents a viable technique for fabricating surfaces with micro- and nanostructures. Its ability to create detailed and reliable patterns over large areas in a single step makes it ideal for scaling up surface engineering [22]. Laser-induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS), in particular, might offer an appropriate topography to decrease microbial adhesion [17,23,24]. LIPSS can be consistently produced with sizes smaller than the laser's wavelength (usually under 1 μm), in a singular procedure, eliminating the need for costly and time-consuming vacuum technologies and lithography [25]. The periodicity of LIPSS can be further controlled by the angle of incidence, fluence or by the applied number of pulses, while the beam polarization corresponds to the direction of LIPSS [26]. While important advancements have been made in the production and design of laser-induced periodic surface structures [27], the ability to generate sub-micron scale surface features across extended areas remains a challenge for large-scale production, throughput optimization and therefore cost reduction. Traditional single-beam approaches typically achieve throughputs of the order of 5 cm^2/min with a high resolution down to ~ 400 nm [27,28].

In the past, several strategies have been explored to overcome the low throughput inherent to conventional LIPSS fabrication. Defocusing the laser beam [29], employing polygon scanners achieving scanning speeds exceeding 100 m/s, or using multi-beam and interference-based methods have been shown to significantly accelerate processing [30,31]. Despite this progress, these approaches often compromise pattern flexibility, require complex synchronization, or result in a loss of the high regularity characteristic of LIPSS patterns. By contrast, dynamic beam shaping using a spatial light modulator (SLM) provides precise, real-time control over the laser wavefront [32,33], enabling the fabrication of customizable micro- and nanostructures without compromising feature fidelity. The adaptability and precision offered by SLM-based dynamic beam shaping could position it as a leading contender for enhancing throughput in LIPSS production. Despite this clear potential, there is still a notable lack of studies exploring the application of SLM-based beam shaping for rapid, large-area nanostructuring aimed at inhibiting yeast adhesion.

In response to these challenges, this study introduces an innovative technology for the rapid fabrication of yeast adhesion-reducing surfaces using dynamic beam shaping with a spatial light modulator. The initial stage focuses on fine-tuning LIPSS topography to evaluate its impact on *S. cerevisiae* adhesion. Additionally, the work explores a novel dual-pass laser process to create hierarchical LIPSS structures, demonstrating significant improvements in processing speed and efficiency. The results highlight the potential of this technology to contribute to improved hygiene and biofilm prevention in various industrial applications.

2. Materials and methods

The present study used stainless steel plates AISI 316L since they are commonly used in the biomedical industry [34]. Prior to laser processing, all samples were cleaned in ethanol and treated in an open atmosphere using a multifunctional multi-beam processing station equipped with a Ytterbium-based diode-pumped solid-state laser system, Perla 100 (HiLASE, Czech Republic) [35], which emits 970 fs pulses with M^2 of 1.1 and a wavelength of 1030 nm. This system generates pulses with energy up to 2 mJ and a repetition rate of 50 kHz. The laser beam was directed through an IntelliSCAN III 14 galvanometric scanner and focussed onto the sample using a 100 mm telecentric F-theta lens, resulting in a spot diameter of 30 μm .

To enhance the nanostructuring process's efficiency, the incoming

laser beam was guided through the dynamic beam shaping unit FBS G3 (Pulsar Photonics GmbH, Germany) equipped with a Spatial Light Modulator (SLM) (Hamamatsu Photonics, Japan) which is able to shape the beam according to the pre-calculated computer-generated hologram (phase-mask) uploaded to the SLM. The output beam was guided into the galvanometric scanner IntelliScan 14 (Scanlab, Germany) and focused on the sample by 100 mm telecentric F-theta lens. In both cases the beam could be displaced on a sample with the maximum scanning speed of 2 m/s. To increase the productivity of nanostructuring the SLM was used to adjust the input beam wavefront by loading the aforementioned computer-generated hologram. This resulted in a top-hat line intensity profile measuring $500 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ (as shown in Fig. 1). The sample received irradiation from a pulse energy of 0.5 mJ, which aligns with the SLM's damage threshold for the employed laser system.

The surface morphology was investigated by laser scanning confocal microscope, Olympus OLS5000 and scanning electron microscope, Tescan MIRA at electron energy of 15 keV. To test the effects of nanostructuring of the metal surface on the adhesion of microorganisms, we used a fluorescent ($p_{\text{TEF}}\text{-GFP}$) derivative of the yeast strain *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* BRF [39,40]. The BRF strain is able to adhere to a plastic surface and form biofilms at the solid-liquid interface [41]. The BRF- $p_{\text{TEF}}\text{-GFP}$ strain was cultured overnight in YE-gal medium (1% yeast extract, 2% galactose), then the cells were washed and seeded in fresh YE-gal medium for 4 h to grow exponentially. The washed cells resuspended in fresh YE-gal were applied at a density of $A_{600} = 0.2$ on the surface of metal plates with micro/nanostructures. After 3 h, the metal plates were washed three times with distilled water to remove non-adherent cells. After complete removal of the liquid and drying, adherent cells were analyzed microscopically (10 \times objective, Leica DMR fluorescent microscope, GFP filter) and surface coverage by adherent cells was quantified using the Image-J program.

3. Results and discussion

With the goal to optimally design the various nanostructured surface morphologies on stainless steel surface for microbial adhesion, it is necessary to determine the optimal laser and processing settings. Based on the past experiences and experiments, it is known that the laser fluence play an important role in LIPSS and setting the fluence just below the ablation threshold is important. Furthermore, the scanning speed and number of laser pulses per unit area were identified as important

Fig. 1. Schematics of the beamshaping setup with insets of input beam, computer generated hologram (phase mask) and final beam at the image plane.

factors influencing the quality and periodicity of Laser-Induced Periodic Surface Structures (LIPSS). The optimization of these parameters resulted in a homogenous structuring of the surface material, characterized by straight and well-defined LIPSS producing nanograting with a periodicity of 940 nm, as shown in Fig. 2. Based on the observed periodicity of 940 nm, which is close to the laser wavelength of 1030 nm, and taking into account their distinct size, orientation, and perpendicular orientation to the laser beam's polarization, these structures fit the typical characteristics of LSFL (low spatial frequency LIPSS) [36]. Different LIPSS structures were seen throughout these studies, depending on the scanning speed and accumulated fluence (fluence times spots per area). Fig. 3 shows how the number of pulses per unit area (PPA) and accumulated fluence became a crucial parameter in the creation of various LIPSS forms.

Fig. 3 demonstrates a clear correlation between the morphological features of LIPSS structures and the number of pulses per unit area at a constant fluence per pulse of 0.7 J/cm^2 . As the number of pulses and the accumulated fluence increase, the LIPSS structures evolve into progressively shorter lines with shorter periodicities. Specifically, optimal LIPSS structures with well-defined periodic grooves are produced with 44 pulses per unit area, resulting in an accumulated fluence of 31 J/cm^2 , and a groove period of 940 nm (Fig. 3a). When the number of pulses increases to 116 and the accumulated fluence to 81 J/cm^2 , the groove length and periodicity significantly decrease to 630 nm (Fig. 3b). With 587 pulses and an accumulated fluence of 411 J/cm^2 , the periodicity further decreases to 360 nm (Fig. 3c). At the highest settings of 1773 pulses and 1241 J/cm^2 , the periodicity reaches its minimum value of 330 nm (Fig. 3d). This progression illustrates how increased pulse counts and accumulated fluence levels contribute to the formation of finer LIPSS structures.

Furthermore, the potential for fabricating hierarchical LIPSS structures became apparent, and Fig. 4 shows that combining fine LIPSS structures with short periodicity with wider periodic LIPSS structures is possible. As shown in Fig. 4, in the first step (Fig. 4a), the LIPSS structure with a periodicity of 630 nm and accumulated fluence of 81 J/cm^2 was produced, followed by a subsequent pass with parameters to produce a well-defined LIPSS with a periodicity of 940 nm (Fig. 4b). A resulting combination as depicted in Fig. 4c and d shows an intriguing structure composed of microgrooves with a periodicity of $5 \mu\text{m}$ covered by a second layer of LIPSS structure with a periodicity of 630 nm. The obtained results can be explained by the fact that, as the pulse number increases, the irradiation of periodic structures on metals can result in the formation of grooves that, unlike LIPSS, no longer follow laser polarization and have a characteristic diameter that is strongly dependent on the fluence used [37]. These structures can be viewed as the result of

early melting of the surface layer [38], followed by rearrangement via temperature gradient relaxation and, finally, the production of hydrodynamic instabilities [39,40].

A comparison was made between the newly introduced fabrication process and more conventional techniques of generating hierarchical structures, building upon the previously indicated methodologies. Rectangular micropillars were created for this purpose by utilizing the conventional beam scanning technique. A UV wavelength was used to reduce the size of these pillars, allowing for a closer focus of the beam and producing micropillars that were $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ in size. Then, 630 nm-periodic LIPSS structures were superimposed on top of these pillars. This led to the formation of a hierarchical structure, as seen in Fig. 5.

Based on the results, three unique structures were selected for further scaling up using beamshaping technology. These include LIPSS with a periodicity of 630 nm, a dual-LIPSS structure combining periodicities of 5 μm and 630 nm, and a LIPSS structure atop UV-light produced micropillars. The LIPSS's 630 nm periodicity is common to all of these selections. This specific scale was chosen for its substantially faster production than smaller LIPSS structures, as well as its possible biological implications due to its sub-micron size. According to the attachment hypothesis, surfaces with features smaller than microbial dimensions can dramatically reduce adhesion to the surface, making this option especially critical in the context of antimicrobial surfaces.

As discussed in earlier section, a small percentage of the available power and pulse energy is used in LIPSS production. It is evident that by reshaping the beam to larger diameters, outcomes similar to the defocused LIPSS processing, as introduced by Mezera et al. [29], can be achieved, leveraging the full potential of the laser system's power and pulse energy. Additionally, if the beam is shaped into a line or rectangle with a homogeneous distribution, less beam overlapping is needed than with a Gaussian beam, allowing for a more effective beam scanning strategy. In order to achieve this, the input Gaussian beam was converted into a line-shaped top-hat beam by computing and then integrating the phase mask, as is depicted in Fig. 6, into the spatial light modulator. The dimensions of this beam shape were meticulously adjusted to harness the maximum pulse energy of 0.5 mJ that the spatial light modulator can accommodate. The resulting beam shape is a top-hat rectangular line measuring $500 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$, enabling significantly faster LIPSS fabrication, as depicted in Fig. 6.

As illustrated in Fig. 6, the LIPSS structures chosen for microbial adhesion analysis were efficiently replicated using a spatial light modulator. Notably, the fabrication speed increased substantially for each structure. For LIPSS with a periodicity of 930 nm, the speed increased from $1.68 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$ to $150 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$. For LIPSS with a periodicity of 630 nm, it went from $0.63 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$ to $57 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$. For the

Fig. 2. Well-defined LIPSS structure with a periodicity of 940 nm produced with a fluence of 0.7 J/cm^2 and 44 pulses per unit area resulting in accumulated fluence of 31 J/cm^2 .

Fig. 3. Evolution of LIPSS generated through a decrease in a scanning speed, resulting in an increase in the number of pulses per unit area (PPA) and a proportional increase in the accumulated fluence. In all cases the fluence per pulse were kept constant at 0.7 J/cm^2 .

Fig. 4. Hierarchical integration of LIPSS showcasing the fabrication process and resultant configurations. (a) Initial LIPSS with a periodicity of 630 nm generated at an accumulated fluence of 81 J/cm^2 . (b) Subsequent formation of LIPSS with a wider periodicity of 940 nm . (c) & (d) Final hierarchical structure featuring microgrooves with a $5 \mu\text{m}$ periodicity overlaid by a finer LIPSS layer with 630 nm periodicity, demonstrating the precise modulation of accumulated fluence to achieve multi-scale surface texturing.

Fig. 5. Hierarchical structure combining standard single beam approach with UV laser to produce rectangular micropillars ($10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$) and 630 nm -periodic LIPSS structure on top of these pillars.

dual-LIPSS structure, the speed rose from $0.42 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$ to $37.4 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$. For the micropillars, beam shaping was not feasible due to the spatial light modulator being designed solely for IR radiation.

Consequently, only the productivity of the second layer, the LIPSS structures, was scaled up in productivity. The overall productivity for the hierarchical structure (micropillars and LIPSS) reached $21 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$, derived from $32 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$ for the pillars alone and $57 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$ for the LIPSS.

A fluorescent version of the *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* yeast strain BRF, which produces the green fluorescent protein GFP (BRF- p_{TEF} -GFP, [40]), was used to study microbial cell adhesion. The BRF strain and its variants adhere to plastic surfaces and form biofilms at the solid-liquid interface [40,41]. To test cell adhesion to modified surfaces, this yeast strain was pre-cultured in YE-gal medium until the exponential growth phase. The cells cultured in this way adhered well to unstructured metal plates (Fig. 7, reference sample). The cells were applied in parallel to metal plates with different micro/nanostructures. After incubation, the surfaces were thoroughly washed (as with the reference sample) to remove planktonic, non-adherent cells, leaving only the cells that adhered to the differently structured surfaces. These adherent cells were then examined under the epifluorescence microscope (Fig. 7).

The microscopy data shed light on the changes in the binding patterns of *S. cerevisiae* BRF- p_{TEF} -GFP cells to different surface morphologies. The visual representation (Fig. 7a–d) shows the patterns of adhesion of the fluorescent cells to differently structured surfaces. Fig. 7e translates these patterns into a comparative metric representing the relative percentage of cell adhesion compared to adhesion on the unstructured metal surface as a reference point.

Based on this observation, a significant reduction in the number of *S. cerevisiae* cells was discerned across all laser-structured surfaces. The most pronounced decrease in adhered cells was observed for the LIPSS structure with a periodicity of 630 nm (Fig. 7b), achieving a reduction of 99.88% compared to the reference sample. For the micropillars overlaid with 630 nm LIPSS, the reduction was slightly lower, at 96.39%, and for the dual-LIPSS structure with $5 \mu\text{m}$ microgrooves, cell adhesion was

Fig. 6. Enhanced LIPSS fabrication via top-hat beam shaping showcasing the fabrication process. (a) Phase mask for beam shaping; (b) Resulting $500 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ top-hat beam; (c) Initial 630 nm LIPSS; (d) Additional 940 nm LIPSS layer; (e) Combined hierarchical structure with 630 nm LIPSS on $5 \mu\text{m}$ microgrooves, all utilizing the top-hat beam.

Fig. 7. (a) Fluorescent microscopy images of *S. cerevisiae* BRF-pTEF-GFP cells adhered to metal plates with different nano/microstructures on the surface including (a) Plane? reference sample. (b) Surface with 630 nm LIPSS. (c) Hierarchical structure with 630 nm LIPSS over $5 \mu\text{m}$ microgrooves. (d) Combination of UV laser-fabricated rectangular micropillars with 630 nm LIPSS. (e) Cell adhesion quantification, comparing the percentage of cells adhering to each structured surface relative to the untreated metal surface.

reduced by 97.56%. Although the hierarchical configurations exhibited slightly diminished microbial reduction effects compared to single LIPSS structures, the additional microstructuring may offer other functional advantages. The incorporation of larger microstructures has been shown in previous studies to influence wettability, where the wetting angle can be controlled by the size and periodicity of microstructures [41]. Additionally, such hierarchical configurations may enhance biocompatibility, as certain cell types can exhibit improved adherence and growth on microstructured surfaces due to increased surface area and topographical cues [42]. Therefore, while the primary benefit of these surfaces remains the reduction of microbial adhesion, the potential for additional functionalities could expand the applicability of this technology, particularly in fields where controlled wettability and biocompatibility are advantageous.

4. Conclusion

This study has showcased a promising approach in the rapid fabrication of yeast adhesion-reducing surfaces using dynamic beam shaping with a spatial light modulator. Through the strategic optimization of LIPSS topography the innovative hierarchical structures with antimicrobial properties were fabricated. Surfaces with a periodicity of 630 nm were created, achieving up to 99.88% reduction in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* adhesion. Additionally, hierarchical structures, combining 630 nm LIPSS with $5 \mu\text{m}$ microgrooves, also showed high effectiveness with over 95% reduction in yeast adhesion. While incorporating

microstructures with the 630 nm LIPSS slightly lowered the adhesion reduction effect (to 97.56% on $5 \mu\text{m}$ microgrooves and 96.39% on square-shaped micropillars), these hierarchical configurations may provide additional functional benefits, such as improved wettability or biocompatibility, making them suitable for broader applications.

The integration of dynamic beam shaping significantly enhanced production speed across all tested structures. The fabrication speed of 930 nm LIPSS was increased from $1.68 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$ to $150 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$, representing an 8800% improvement. Similarly, for 630 nm LIPSS, the speed rose from $0.63 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$ to $57 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$, marking a 9000% enhancement. Even dual-LIPSS structures saw substantial gains, with productivity increasing from $0.42 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$ to $37.4 \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}$. These enhancements validated the scalability and industrial applicability of this approach for large-scale production, offering a scalable method for creating biofilm-resistant surfaces with rapid production capabilities. The findings have important implications for industries that prioritize hygienic and biofilm-resistant surfaces, such as healthcare and food processing.

Data availability

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, PH, ZP, LV, VP Methodology, PH, ZP, LV, RB, MP, VP, JB, MC, TM, MS, IT, SP, JM, ZF, MK, JS, MF; Validation, PH, ZP, LV, RB, MP, VP, JB, MC, TM, MS, IT, SP, JM, ZF, MK, JS, MF; Investigation, PH, ZP, LV, VP, IT; Writing - Original Draft, PH, SP Writing - Review & Editing, PH, ZP, LV, RB, MP, JB, MC, TM, MS, SP, JM, ZF, MK, JS, MF, Visualization, PH, ZP, LV; Project administration, PH, ZP; Funding acquisition, TM, ZP.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT by OpenAI to assist in refining the language of the manuscript. After using this tool, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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